

Original article

Determination of stomata type in some members of the Brassicaceae family: A Cross-Sectional Study.

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Abstract

Background: The Brassicaceae family, comprising economically important species like *Raphanus sativus* and *Brassica oleracea*, exhibits distinct stomatal characteristics relevant to plant physiology and taxonomy. **Aim:** This study investigated the stomatal types, and distribution of *Brassica oleracea capitata*, *Brassica oleracea botrytis*, and *Raphanus sativus*. **Materials and Methods:** Leaf samples were collected from Kasuwar Turawa Yankaba, Nassarawa Local Government, Kano State, Nigeria. Epidermal peels from both abaxial and adaxial surfaces were prepared, stained with 1% aqueous safranin, and examined microscopically at ×400 magnification. **Results:** The results showed that all three species possess anisocytic (cruciferous type) stomata and are amphistomatic; the abaxial side has a higher density than the adaxial side. **Conclusion:** This distribution pattern aligns with previous reports on dicot leaf anatomy and suggests an adaptive mechanism to reduce photoinhibition by limiting excessive exposure on the more sunlight-exposed adaxial surface. These findings provide additional anatomical evidence for the taxonomic placement of the studied species within Brassicaceae and contribute to understanding their physiological adaptations.

Keywords: *Brassicaceae*, *Brassica oleracea botrytis*, *Brassica oleracea capitata*, *Raphanus sativus*, Stomata.

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Introduction

Brassicaceae (/bræsɪ'keɪsɪi/) or Cruciferae (/kru:'sɪfəri/) is a medium-sized and commercially significant family of flowering plants commonly known as the mustards, the crucifers, or the cabbage family.¹ Some members grow as shrubs, although the majority are herbaceous. Their leaves are grouped in rosettes or alternately arranged without stipules; they are usually simple, though they can be heavily lobed. The plants bear terminal inflorescences lacking bracts, with flowers consisting of four separate sepals, four alternating free petals, and six stamens- two short and four long. Usually, the fruit has rows of seeds with a thin partition (septum) between them. There are 4060 recognized species and 372 genera in the family.² The biggest genera in the family include *Cardamine* (233 species), *Erysimum* (261 species), *Lepidium* (234 species), *Alyssum* (207 species), and *Draba* (approximately 440 species).

The cruciferous vegetable family includes species including *Brassica rapa* (turnip, Chinese cabbage, and allied crops), *Brassica napus* (rapeseed), *Raphanus sativus* (radish), *A Armoracia rusticana* (horseradish), and *Brassica oleracea* (broccoli, cabbage, cauliflower, kale, and collards).³ It also includes attractive plants such as the commonly

used research model *Arabidopsis thaliana* (thale cress) and *Matthiola* (stock). Notably, commercially grown Brassicaceae species are known to be seriously harmed by *Pieris rapae* and other butterflies in the Pieridae family. Due to its resistance to widely used pest control techniques, the *Trichoplusia ni* (cabbage looper) moth is also becoming a bigger problem for crucifers.³ Native mustards are essential to the survival of some less common *Pieris* butterflies, such as *Pieris virginianensis*, in their natural environments. However, some introduced mustards can be toxic or hazardous to their larvae, such as garlic mustard (*Alliaria petiolata*), which is very invasive in the US.³

A stoma (plural "stomata"), also called a stomate (plural "stomata") (from Greek στόμα, "mouth"), is a pore, present in the epidermis of leaves, stems, and other organs, that enables gas exchange.⁴ Two guard cells are specialized parenchyma cells that encircle the stomata and control the opening and closing of the stomata. These pores respond to the light conditions and osmotic variations, enabling the intake of CO₂ required for photosynthesis.⁴

There are various stoma type classifications. A popular one is based on the kinds introduced by Julien Joseph Vesque, which were then expanded upon by Metcalfe & Chalk,⁵ and later enhanced by other writers.⁶ The size, shape, and arrangement of the subsidiary cells around the pair of guard cells determine this. Among them are:

1) Anomocytic stomata (irregular-celled) are characterized by guard cells encircled by epidermal cells that are comparable in size, shape, and arrangement to the rest of the epidermis. This stomatal type, also known as the ranunculaceous type, is found in more than a hundred dicot families, such as the Apocynaceae, Boraginaceae, Chenopodiaceae, and Cucurbitaceae.

2) Anisocytic stomata. Guard cells are flanked by two bigger subsidiary cells and one notably smaller one in anisocytic stomata (unequal-celled). They are also referred to as the cruciferous type and are found in more than thirty dicot families, including *Crassulaceae*, *Solanaceae*, and *Brassicaceae*.

3) Paracytic stomata; One or more subsidiary cells oriented parallel to the guard cell opening define paracytic stomata, also known as parallel-celled stomata. These cells could stay shorter or grow longer than the guard cells. This type, also known as the rubiaceus type, is found in over a hundred dicot families, including *Fabaceae*, *Convolvulaceae*, and *Rubiaceae*.

4) Diacytic stomata; Cross-celled diacytic stomata are made up of guard cells that border two

subsidiary cells. These cells wrap around one end of the pore and meet across from the centre of the aperture. This kind of stomata, also known as the caryophyllaceous type, is found in more than ten dicot families, including *Acanthaceae* and *Caryophyllaceae*

Materials and Methods

Study area

The study was conducted at the Plant Physiology Laboratory, located at the Faculty of Life Sciences, Bayero University, Kano, Nigeria. The laboratory is located at the old site campus of the university. The old site campus is located at coordinates 11.9809 degrees North and 8.4826 degrees East.

Sample Collection

The leaves of *Brassica oleracea capitata*, *Brassica oleracea botrytis*, and *Raphanus sativus* were collected at Kasuwar Turawa Yankaba, Nassarawa Local Government of Kano State. Fresh, healthy, and mature leaves were collected from the plant species under study. Mature leaves are preferred, as they possess fully developed epidermal features, unlike juvenile or senescent leaves, which may display abnormal stomatal patterns.^{7,8}

Epidermal Peel

Small sections (1–2 cm²) were excised from the median portion of the leaf blade. The mesophyll tissue was carefully scraped away using a razor blade to expose the epidermis. The peel was washed with distilled water to remove debris.^{9,10}

Staining and Mounting

After being dyed for three to five minutes with 1% aqueous safranin O, the epidermal peel was washed with distilled water and preserved in a 10% glycerol solution. To prevent air bubbles, a cover slip was carefully placed over the sample.¹¹

Microscopic Observation

Slides were examined under a compound microscope at ×100 and ×400 magnification. Stomatal types were identified based on the arrangement of subsidiary cells following the classification system developed by Vesque¹² and modified by Metcalfe & Chalk.⁵

Results

The type of stomata found in all three species is anisocytic. The species studied were *Raphanus sativus*, *Brassica oleracea capitata*, and *Brassica oleracea botrytis*. Figures 1 and 2 below show anisocytic

stomata found on the underside of *Raphanus sativus* and *Brassica oleracea botrytis*, respectively.

Figure 1: Anisocytic stomata (a) found in the lower surface of *Raphanus sativus* (x400) μm

Figure 2: Anisocytic stomata (a) found in the lower surface of *Brassica oleracea botrytis* (x400) μm

Discussion

In this study, leaf epidermal structures of the three members of the family *Brassicaceae* were studied based on the occurrence of stomata. The species have stomata that occur on both abaxial and adaxial surfaces and are termed Amphistomatic,¹³ Muir (2015), who works on making pore choices. In all three species, the stomata found were Anisocytic,⁶ the same as the findings of Metcalfe & Chalk,⁵ who work on the anatomy of dicots; that is, stomata encircled by three cells, one of which was noticeably larger or smaller than the other two (unequal-celled). On the abaxial surface, there are more stomata than on the adaxial surface.^{7,8} The

stomata distribution shows that the stomata are more numerous in the lower surface than in the upper surface of all the species studied. Both the upper and lower surfaces of the species under study have amphistomatic leaves, or stomata, with the abaxial side having a larger density.¹⁴ Since the adaxial surface is more exposed to solar radiation^{4,5} because the majority of the leaves are in the horizontal position, amphistomatic leaves typically have a greater number of stomata in the epidermis of the abaxial surface,¹⁵ this appears to be a defence mechanism against photoinhibition.

The present study revealed that *Brassica oleracea capitata*, *Brassica oleracea botrytis*, and *Raphanus sativus*, all members of the *Brassicaceae* family, possess anisocytic (cruciferous type) stomata and are amphistomatic, occurring on both adaxial and abaxial leaf sides. In all species, the abaxial surface exhibited a higher stomatal density and stomatal index compared to the adaxial surface. This pattern is consistent with previous anatomical studies of dicotyledonous leaves and likely represents an adaptive feature that minimizes photoinhibition by reducing excessive exposure of stomata to direct sunlight on the upper surface. The observed uniformity of stomatal type within the studied taxa reinforces the value of stomatal morphology as a reliable taxonomic character in *Brassicaceae*. These findings enhanced the understanding of the leaf anatomical features of these economically important species and provide baseline data that may support further physiological, ecological, and taxonomic research.

Conclusion

The present study revealed that *Brassica oleracea capitata*, *Brassica oleracea botrytis*, and *Raphanus sativus*, all members of the *Brassicaceae* family, possess anisocytic (cruciferous type) stomata and are amphistomatic, bearing stomata on both lower (abaxial) and upper (adaxial) leaf sides. These findings provide additional anatomical evidence for the taxonomic placement of the studied species within *Brassicaceae* and contribute to understanding their physiological adaptations.

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